

Comparison of Instructional System Development (ISD) with
Systems Engineering from the Training System Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Instructional system development (ISD) is a process which has been used for development of training courseware. Systems engineering is a process which has been used for systematic development of training device hardware and software to support the courseware. The recent expansion of the training system concept to encompass the full life cycle of training for aircrew and maintenance personnel within a weapon system has brought about an integration of the traditional ISD process with the systems engineering process. This integration has brought team members from seemingly different disciplines together, resulting in some confusion and unnecessary discord. The purpose of this paper is to resolve this confusion by comparing the ISD process with the systems engineering process from the training system perspective. The authors conclude that one process is really a derivative of the other. With this understanding, the necessary integration of ISD with systems engineering should be facilitated.

INTRODUCTION

The last decade has seen a significant change in the way training systems are designed, developed and procured. The recommendation of the 1982 Scientific Advisory Board to apply state-of-the-art technology to the training process resulted in the C-130 Model Aircrew Training System (MATS) study contracted to Seville Training Systems by Air Force Human Resources Laboratory. This study used the Instructional Systems Development (ISD) process to develop the entire training system model for C-130 aircrew training. In addition, the Office of Management and Budget Circular A-76 suggesting a "civilianization" of the Air Force, and the conversion of 85% of the simulator instructor authorizations to civilian positions in 1985 by the Air Staff, combined to clear the way for the totally contracted Aircrew Training System (ATS). This new approach to the development and procurement of training for aircrew members, plus the emphasis on concurrency between the training system and the airframe, required the integration of two processes, ISD and systems engineering. Previously these processes had been accomplished separately in training system acquisition. Systems engineering had been

used for years to design and develop the simulator and training device components of the training system. Since the 1970s, ISD had been used to design and develop the instruction that incorporated these devices. The advancement in training simulator capabilities with the advent of the full scale weapon system trainer (WST) had a significant impact on training system design. Independent development of the WST through systems engineering without consideration through ISD of how the WST would be integrated into the training system resulted in a less than optimum use of a very capable training media (Bills & Nullmeyer 1985). When it came time to use the WST for training, the extensive capabilities built into the WST were untried. Training managers attempted to sandwich the WST into an already compact curriculum (Bills, 1987).

The totally contracted ATS for the new C-17 and ATF weapon system acquisitions created the opportunity to integrate the systems engineering and the ISD processes to capitalize on new training technology. The two processes are being required to mesh with each other to produce a training system that optimizes training effectiveness and efficiency. Each process follows similar logical steps. In fact the ISD process was initially derived from the systems engineering process.

COMPARISON OF ISD and SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

ISD was initially used as a process in training system courseware development (AFR 50-8). It provided a systematic approach for decision making. The extension of this ISD process to a fully integrated training system perspective caused an adjustment to the initial process. The process is an iterative logical sequence for deriving the performance tasks and associated skills, knowledges, and attitudes to perform the mission requirements. The process guides the definition of training requirements, the objectives for achieving the requirements, and the training media and associated courseware syllabus for achieving the objectives. The process provides for design, development and production with a continual feedback loop for assessment and revision as required. The function of ISD is to control the instructional system design process for the purpose of achieving an integrated and optimum balance of all system elements.

Table 1

Comparison of the Systems Engineering Process
With the Instructional Systems Development Process

Systems Engineering	ISD
Determine Objectives and Performance Specifications: - user needs - work flow - organizational characteristics - user characteristics	Analyze System Requirements: - user needs - job performance - entry levels - organizational conditions - define mission/tasks
Define System: - define functional req'ts - define operational req'ts	Define Education or Training Requirements: - define instruction needed - define skills, knowledges, and attitudes - define performance criteria
Design System: - allocate functions - design work proceedings - design performance feedback	Develop Objectives and Tests: - allocate training req'ts to objectives - devise criterion tests
Interface Design: - design interface - design work areas	Plan, Develop and Validate Instruction: - define media - design syllabus - develop courseware - conduct small group tryouts
Evaluate: - test specifications - conduct testing - system evaluation	Evaluate: - evaluate instruction - evaluate graduate performance - system evaluation

Systems engineering is the application of scientific and engineering effort to transform an operational need into a description of system parameters or requirements and the preferred system configuration for effectiveness (AFR 800-13). The systems engineering process is an iterative logical sequence that determines the objectives and performance specifications and further defines the functional and operational requirements. These requirements are then used to allocate functions and design appropriate mechanisms to achieve the operational need, with a continual feedback loop to verify and modify as required. The function of systems engineering is to control the entire design process for the purpose of achieving an integrated and optimum balance of all system elements.

Systems engineering and ISD are parallel processes that produce a similar output. Both processes begin with input, go through translation and analysis, accomplish trade-offs, go through synthesis, and result in output. Therefore, by comparing the two processes from the training system perspective one can determine the associated activities which can be integrated into one useful process.

From the training system perspective, the systems engineering process can be broken down into five activities as follows: (1) Determine objectives and performance specifications, (2) Define functional and operational requirements, (3) Allocate functions, (4) Design interface, and (5) Evaluation (Baily, 1982). The ISD process can also be broken down into five activities as follows: (1) Analyze system, (2) Define training requirement, (3) Develop objectives, (4) Plan, develop, and validate, and (5) Evaluation. The following step by step comparison of the traditional wording used in the systems engineering activities with that of the ISD activities is to derive similarities in functional meaning.

Step one: The systems engineering process translates the user needs into objectives and performance specifications. This translation determines work flow and organizational and user characteristics. The ISD process translates the user needs into system requirements. This translation defines job performance requirements, entry level characteristics, and organizational conditions. This step is almost identical for both processes since the procedures translate user

needs into the parameters associated with the system.

Step two: The systems engineering process performs an analysis which defines functional and operational requirements. The ISD process performs an analysis which defines what instruction is needed and the type required. Step two for both disciplines is to do a functional analysis and break the system requirements into parts in order to define what is needed.

Step three: The systems engineering process accomplishes trade-off analysis to allocate functions, design work proceedings and design a performance feedback mechanism. The ISD process defines instruction needed and performs trade-off analysis to allocate training tasks to objectives. Each objective has a criterion for feedback on achievement of the objective. Both systems engineering and ISD are using trade-off analysis for allocating activities and techniques to accomplish each activity and a feedback mechanism to verify performance.

Step four: Through the systems engineering process, a synthesis results in design of interfaces and the associated work areas. Through the ISD process, synthesis results in the instructional syllabus and supporting courseware. Again, both procedures accomplish a synthesis of the activities and techniques derived in step three. The main thrust is to develop the appropriate interfaces to attain system effectiveness.

Step five: The systems engineering process evaluates the final product against the system specifications and conducts testing to verify that the baseline performance requirements were achieved. The ISD process evaluates the training system against the system objectives and evaluates graduates to see if they meet the baseline job performance requirements. Both processes attempt to evaluate if the optimal solution has been achieved by evaluating the product of the system and measuring effectiveness against the desired level of performance.

This comparison illustrates that the ISD process is in fact a derivative of the systems engineering process. Traditional wording used in the systems approach to develop training systems should not hinder the future coexistence of ISD and systems engineering during training system acquisition. This notion is easily achieved if the language barrier can be alleviated. Functionally, the first step in each process is a translation of the user needs into parameters associated with the system. The second step is an analysis to define the system requirements. Third, each process accomplishes trade-offs to derive activities and techniques to accomplish them, with a feedback loop to check performance. The synthesis in the fourth step of each process produces the derived techniques and system interfaces. The final step is an evaluation of whether or not the optimal solution has been achieved. Thus, this bridge of the language gap

can redirect former efforts to gain understanding of one another to a more productive common focus on the training system problem at hand.

CONCLUSION

The ISD and systems engineering processes are really derivatives of each other and can be integrated in the acquisition of training systems for new weapon systems. The once perceived disconnect between the ISD community and systems engineering community is more semantic than a real difference in each discipline's processes. By coming to a common understanding of terms, both communities can be integrated without barriers. Translation, analysis, trade-offs, synthesis, test and evaluation are terms that can facilitate this interaction when systems engineering and ISD must come together in training system acquisition. Application of this approach should be an iterative process, continuing from acquisition through the life cycle of the weapon system.

REFERENCES

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